

From virtual classroom to radiology department: A correlation study of the student's academic performance in radiographic positioning and radiologic procedures course vs practical performances during face-to-face internship

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Abstract

In online classes, it will be rather difficult to teach radiographic positioning and radiologic procedures through discussions, video, and/or images. Moreover, it is fair enough to be worried whether the students have truly learned the said course. With that, the aim of this study is to determine the correlation of the grades of the fourth-year students enrolled in the radiologic positioning and radiographic procedure courses from the second semester of the academic year 2020–2021. This result was compared to their actual evaluation during a face-to-face internship in the Radiology department at St. Dominic Medical Center Inc., Bacoor, Cavite, Philippines. The researcher utilized a quantitative non-experimental correlational design and a purposive sampling that included the entire position. Therefore, it accumulated a total of 17 respondents. Based on the findings, a Pearson-r value of 0.6 shows a strong correlation between the variables. With a computed p-value of 0.01 that is lower than the 0.05 significance level, results suggest that there is a positive correlation between the two variables. Therefore, the higher the grades in the radiographic positioning and radiologic procedures course, the better the performance during face-to-face internships.

Keywords: Radiologic technology; Face-to-face internship; Radiographic positioning; Radiologic procedures; Grades.

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Introduction

A radiographer is a medical profession that deals with manipulating different medical imaging, which aims to provide radiographs that will help physicians and specialists in the diagnosing process. One way to ensure that a radiographer can produce an accurate image is by doing the proper radiographic positioning and different radiologic procedures inside the exposure room area.

With the COVID-19 pandemic still going on, there are still quite a few students, together with the influence of their families, mostly prepared to have their classes done online. The downside of doing so is the practical application of those subjects that need to have hands-on practice with the proper guidance of an authorized individual, such as the professors.

Researchers from different studies talked about the advantages and disadvantages of online learning. Having flexible schedules, more convenience from homes, and being safer from COVID-19 were some of the notable benefits of doing online classes (Ferri et al., 2020; Hebebcı et al., 2020; Kohnke & Moorhouse, 2021; Popa et al., 2020). Meanwhile, being more expensive, more prone to distractions, and lacking social engagement were some of the obvious disadvantages of virtual classes (Comer & Lenaghan, 2013; Ma & Lee, 2019; Octaberlina & Muslimin, 2020). There are some activities, such as laboratory experiments, that will require the use of equipment that cannot be performed by students in an online setting (Babinčáková & Bernard, 2020; Tatlı & Ayas, 2013). That will result in a lack of practical knowledge due to online education.

In online classes, it will be rather difficult to teach radiographic positioning and radiologic procedures through discussions, video, and/or images. Moreover, it is fair enough to be worried whether students have truly learned the said course. With that, the researcher started this study by correlating the grades the students got in the radiologic positioning and radiographic procedures from the fourth-year students enrolled in the second semester of academic year 2020–2021. This finding would also compare the results of their actual evaluation during a face-to-face internship in the Radiology department at St. Dominic Medical Center Inc., Bacoor, Cavite, Philippines.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual framework

This framework used the two-way interaction model of the grades of radiographic positioning and radiologic procedures courses and face-to-face internship evaluation of students from the Bachelor of Science in Radiologic Technology of St. Dominic College of Asia. According to Al-Rammah (2018), radiological sciences students have increased their satisfaction with their clinical training and have acquired their skills in other subjects. It helps interns or graduating students to be prepared in requesting and interpreting diagnostic radiology investigations for their patients (Glenn-Cox et al., 2019).

Methodology

The researcher utilized a quantitative non-experimental correlational design that describes social phenomena but does not include manipulation from an independent variable. According to Curtis et al. (2016), a correlational research design focuses on the relationships between variables without using any control or manipulation of them. This research design usually ends with either positive or negative.

The study used three sources of data. The primary sources of data were the scores that the fourth-year level students have gotten during their virtual classes in radiographic positioning and radiologic procedures. The secondary sources were the scores from their face-to-face internship evaluation. While the tertiary sources of data include books, online journals, and the internet, from which other facts, information, and studies were drawn.

By utilizing a purposive sampling that includes the entire position, the researcher was able to accumulate a total of 17 respondents, mainly fourth-year students from BS Radiologic Technology enrolled at St. Dominic College of Asia. In addition, it compiled the students' scores from radiographic positioning and radiologic procedures courses and face-to-face internship evaluation. The researcher assured the respondents that all data gathered will only be for research purposes and will not cause any harm to the research study. A t-test was conducted at the 0.05 level of significance to determine if the scores from radiographic positioning and radiologic procedures courses and face-to-face internship evaluation are correlated with each other.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Students' scores in radiographic positioning and radiologic procedures courses and face-to-face internship evaluation

Student Number	Radiographic Positioning and Radiologic Procedures Grades	Face-to-Face Internship Evaluation Scores
1	86	90
2	87	93
3	95	100
4	86	100
5	88	100
6	89	93
7	83	100
8	86	93
9	75	83
10	84	97
11	82	90
12	97	93
13	84	90
14	91	100
15	92	100
16	83	92
17	80	90

Table 1 shows the scores from radiographic positioning and radiologic procedures courses and face-to-face internship evaluation. It can be noticed from the table that student #3 earned the highest score for radiographic positioning and radiologic procedures courses with a frequency of 95. Furthermore, some students (Students #3, #4, #5, #7, #14, and #15) got a perfect score (f = 100) based on face-to-face internship evaluation. Results also showed that student #9 has made the lowest score of 75 in radiographic positioning and radiologic procedures courses and 83 in face-to-face internship evaluation. All except one student (Student #12) improved their skills in conducting different imaging examinations and related their experience to understanding in the classrooms. This shows that students have increased their abilities in performing radiographic procedures. By taking a comprehensive view of their existing initiatives that promote critical thinking and active learning, training programs can move from a traditional hospital-based organized teaching technique to a wider range of practice environments (Morrissey & Heilbrun, 2017).

Table 2. Statistics tools

Statistics tools	Frequency
Coefficient (r)	0.598920253
N	17
T-statistic:	2.89658222
df	15
p-value	0.011071141
Level of Significance	0.05

In Table 2, which shows the statistics tools, based on the findings, a Pearson-r value of 0.6 shows a strong positive correlation between the variables. With a computed p-value of 0.01 that is lower than the 0.05 significance level, it suggests that there is a positive correlation between the two variables. Therefore, higher grades in the radiographic positioning and radiologic procedures courses will give better results in their performance during face-to-face internship.

This result is somehow supported by the study conducted by Paul and Jefferson (2019). The results of their study showed that there was no significant difference in the student performance between online and face-to-face learners. This can simply mean that regardless of the platforms used in education, it will not have a great impact on the learnings of the students. But of course, professors should be more creative and add more efforts to really allow the students to learn the topics, especially if it involves practical knowledge.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The data shows that professors in the Radiologic Technology department who handled the radiographic positioning and radiologic procedures did well because it does not affect their performances in handling a real patient during their face-to-face internship. Knowing that, it is recommended to conduct a series of simulation activities to help the students visualize what they will encounter once working inside the hospital.

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